

Design and Implementation of a Low-Cost Smart Egg Incubation System

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ABSTRACT

The design and construction of a smart egg incubator employing a DHT (Digital Humidity and Temperature) 11 sensor and the ESP8266 (Espressif Systems) microcontroller are presented in this study. An intelligent, automated environment is provided by the incubator for successful egg hatching. Because the ESP8266 has wireless communication, users can utilise a mobile application to remotely monitor and manage the incubator. The bulb provides heat while the fan maintains sufficient air movement to maintain the ideal temperature and humidity levels. Temperature and humidity sensors are used in the system to precisely control the inside climate, ensuring ideal conditions for egg incubation. For poultry farms, this affordable and effective method provides ease and higher hatch rates.

KEYWORDS:ESP 8266, bulb, fan, low cost, DHT 11,incubator, automatic control

1. INTRODUCTION

Embryonic development in eggs occurs in three phases: differentiation, growth, and maturation. During the early stage, organ formation takes place, followed by growth and maturation, which require precise environmental conditions. As the embryo develops, its metabolic activity increases, leading to higher heat production. Maintaining optimal incubator conditions is essential for successful hatching.

An egg incubator is designed to regulate temperature and humidity for proper embryonic development. Incubation can be natural, where a broody hen maintains the required conditions, or artificial, where an incubator provides a controlled environment. Artificial incubators use thermostats to regulate conditions, making them more efficient for large-scale hatching. This study focuses on designing a low-cost smart incubator with IoT (Internet of Things)-based monitoring and control.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Kyeremeh and Peprah in [1] had designed and constructed of an Arduino Microcontroller-based egg incubator which controlled heaters, air circulation fans and mechanism for turning trays, through relays. A Novel Fully Automated Incubation, Manipulation and Documentation System for the Avian Embryogenesis is designed by Schmitt [2]. Moreover, a Low-Cost Domestic Incubator for Hatching Japanese Quail Eggs designed by Deka et al. [3]. Smart eggs incubator system is reported by Omar et al. [4]. Ohpagu and Nwous reported a temperature control egg incubator for various kind of eggs [5].

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Hardware Design:

In mechanical design is focus on construction of the SEIS. It starts with the built of the casing. The material was used are glass fiber coated with cardboard. It is because, is preferable rather than softer wood. This Smart Egg Incubator can fill up to 8-10 eggs. 1 bulb is placed attached to the roof inside of the Smart Egg Incubator. The 100 Watts bulb is used to supply heat to the eggs. The 16x2 LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) is used to display the temperature and humidity for constant monitoring. There are two layers for

the Smart Egg Incubator that call first layer and second layer. First layer is where amount of eggs are placed. It is main casing with the egg tray, bulbs and fan. For the second layer, it is for the controller system. It will control the temperature, fan, bulbs and humidity. [3]

3.2 Software Design:

The ESP8266 is a low cost Wi-Fi microchip that manages the control firmware and Incubator system operation. The ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi microcontroller that enables devices to connect to the internet, making it suitable for IoT projects and wireless communication applications. The program's environment is written in embedded C, but it simplifies it to be an easy-to-use program. The code uploaded to the ESP 8266 controls the temperature and humidity of the DHT11 by reading. The resulting humidity and temperature is also displayed on the LCD screen. Considering that something malfunctioned during the incubation, an error message appears on the LCD Panel.[3]

The maximum temperature in Smart Egg Incubator should be 37 °C and the minimum temperature should be 35 °C. Lamp will be on until the temperature achieves 37 °C. At 37 °C, the lamp will be off and the fan will be on until temperature decrease to 35 °C. At 35 °C, the fan will be off and the lamp will on until the temperature increase to 37 °C. So, the range of temperature in Smart Egg Incubator will be maintained between 35 °C to 37 °C. [3]

3.3 Components Required:

ESP 8266, DHT 11, Adaptor, 2-channel relay module, Cooling fan, Bulb, Fiber box, 16*2 LCD display

Figure 1. Hardware Components

3.4 Process logic

The block diagram depicts the total blue print of the proposed project, A Smart Egg Incubator. The total functioning of the project is represented in a single block diagram as shown. ESP 8266 is the brain of this system. DHT 11 is the humidity and temperature sensor, which is connected to the ESP 8266. A 16*2 LCD display is connected to the ESP 8266 to view the current temperature and humidity conditions inside the incubator. The desired temperature and humidity of the incubator is achieved by using two separate fans in an appropriate manner, which are also interfaced with the processor. The smart phone is interfaced with ESP 8266 through Wi-Fi. Using smartphone, the current values of temperature and humidity can be monitored through googlespread sheets [5].

Figure 2. Block Diagram of entire process

3.5 Data Modelling

1. Egg Incubator Settings:

Target Temperature: The desired temperature for egg incubation is 35°C to 37°C.

Target Humidity: The desired humidity level for optimal incubation is 50% to 60%.

Turning Interval: The time interval between egg turning cycles is 4 hours.

2. Environmental Data:

Temperature: The current temperature inside the incubator.

Humidity: The current humidity level inside the incubator.

3. Egg Data:

Egg Count: The total number of eggs present in the incubator is 4.

Egg Status: We have 4 fertile eggs and all 4 are developing.

Egg Turned: All the eggs are turned after for every 4 hours.

4. Device Status:

Device Health: The status of the incubator device is online for 24*7.

4. SAFETY ISSUES

While smart egg incubators offer numerous benefits, there are some safety issues that need to be addressed. Firstly, the electrical components, such as the ESP8266 microcontroller, fan, and bulb, should be properly installed and wired to avoid short circuits or electrical hazards. Secondly, the heat generated by the bulb can pose a fire risk if not adequately controlled or if flammable materials are present nearby. Thirdly, the wireless connectivity of the ESP8266 should be secured to prevent unauthorized access or tampering.

5. RESULT ANALYSIS

5.1 Day to Day Average values

DAY	DATE	HUMIDITY	TEMP(°C)	TEMP(°F)
1	13/05/2023	62.52	36.14	97.06
2	14/05/2023	57.39	36.10	96.99
3	15/05/2023	60.38	36.08	96.94
4	16/05/2023	68.96	36.08	96.94
5	17/05/2023	74.15	36.08	96.94
6	18/05/2023	70.08	36.10	96.97
7	19/05/2023	69.21	36.17	97.11
8	20/05/2023	69.21	36.10	96.98
9	21/05/2023	76.13	36.17	97.10
10	22/05/2023	74.05	36.10	96.97
11	23/05/2023	66.78	36.14	97.05
12	24/05/2023	61.44	36.07	96.93
13	25/05/2023	67.41	36.16	97.08
14	26/05/2023	61.60	36.21	97.18
15	27/05/2023	64.28	36.21	97.18
16	28/05/2023	65.12	36.24	97.24
17	29/05/2023	69.04	36.25	97.26
18	30/05/2023	73.46	36.27	97.29
19	31/05/2023	74.33	36.27	97.29
21	01/06/2023	74.59	36.27	97.28
22	02/06/2023	77.46	36.37	97.46
23	03/06/2023	78.23	36.30	97.34

Table 1. Day to day average values of different parameter

5.2 Changes in Eggs over the period

- At first, we tried the experiment with the eggs found in local market (not fertile). After 5 days of incubating, we observed no difference when done candle light test.

Figure 3. Eggs from market showing no change after 5 days

- Then 4 fertile eggs were taken, image showing the changes,

Figure 4.Changes in Egg1

Figure 5. Changes in Egg2

Figure 6.Changes in Egg3

Figure 7. Changes in Egg4

- After 27 days ,two eggs have shown crack , called popping

eggs

Figure 8. Showing cracks on two

6. CONCLUSION

The smart egg incubator provides a cost-effective and efficient solution for hatching eggs, ensuring optimal environmental conditions. IoT-based monitoring enhances convenience and control. However, limitations include restricted wireless range, dependency on a stable power supply, and limited scalability due to the ESP8266's constraints. Future improvements could involve integrating advanced sensors for precise climate control and enhancing remote monitoring capabilities.

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